

Nature of Metal Chloride Complexes in Organic Solvent Media. Part I—Iron(III)

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The nature of Fe(III) species that exist in different organic solvent systems like ethanol, DMSO and acetone are investigated. Ion-exchange, conductivity and spectral studies indicate the Fe(III) species as anionic FeCl_4^- in ethanol, cationic FeCl^{++} in DMSO and polymeric $(\text{FeCl}_6)_x$ in acetone.

THE anion exchange uptake of Fe(III) from organic solvent media containing hydrochloric acid has been investigated by several workers¹⁻⁴. Studies in this laboratory showed that the anion exchange uptake of Fe(III) increased with addition of methanol and ethanol, but there was a sharp decrease with acetone and with DMSO (dimethyl sulfoxide). From this it appears that the nature of the Fe(III) species differs with the solvent medium. This is further confirmed by conductometric, spectrophotometric and far I.R. studies. We describe some of our studies in this communication.

Experimental

Ion-exchange Resin: Amberlite IRA-400 "Analytical grade" anion exchange resin (-70 +100 mesh) of Rohm and Haas was used in the chloride form.

Metal solution: A 0.05M stock solution of ferric chloride was prepared from E. Merck sample of $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and standardised against standard EDTA solution⁵.

Tetramethyl Ammonium Tetrachloroferrate (III) (TMATCF): The complex TMATCF was prepared according to the procedure of Cotton and Goodgame⁶.

Organic solvents: All the solvents were purified by standard methods.

Radioactive tracer: γ -active iron (^{59}Fe $t_{1/2} = 45$ days) was obtained from Bhabha Atomic Research Centre as FeCl_3 in HCl solution with a specific activity of 4 Ci per g.

Equipment

Conductivity measurements: A Philips model PR 9500/90 direct measuring conductivity bridge with a magic eye indicator giving an accuracy of $\pm 2.5\%$ was used. The measurements were carried out at $28.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Spectrophotometric measurements: Visible and ultraviolet spectra were taken on a UVSPEK spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched silica cells. I.R. Spectra were obtained on a Beckman-12 I.R. Spectrophotometer.

Radioactivity measurements: The ^{59}Fe γ -activity was estimated with a NaI(Tl) scintillation crystal coupled to a single channel γ -ray spectrometer (ECIL Model GRS 20 B).

Distribution coefficient values K_d : Distribution coefficients for Fe(III) were determined by batch equilibration method using the equation⁷

$$K_d = \frac{\text{Volume of the solution in ml}}{\text{Weight of the resin in g.}} \times \frac{\text{Activity on the resin}}{\text{Activity in the solution}}$$

Results

Ion-exchange studies: The K_d values for Fe(III) as a function of organic solvent concentration in different organic solvents (methanol, ethanol, acetone and DMSO)-hydrochloric acid-water systems are given in figure 1 from which it is seen that while the anion exchange uptake of Fe(III) from hydrochloric acid solution containing methanol or ethanol is high, the uptake is negligible in acetone and DMSO. It is also observed that when acetone or DMSO is added to the alcohol-HCl system the high K_d values obtaining in the alcohol-HCl systems showed a marked decrease in uptake (Fig. 2).

Conductance studies: The molar conductance (Λ_M) values of the TMATCF complex in various solvents at 0.001M concentration (Table 1) show that it behaves as 1:1 electrolyte in the solvents ethanol and acetone. On the other hand in DMSO the value is nearer to a 1:2 electrolyte value.

Spectrophotometric studies: The spectra of the complex TMATCF in ethanol and DMSO in 200–400 nm region are given in Fig. 3. The spectral

Fig. 1. Anion exchange uptake of Fe(III) from solvent systems.

Fig. 2. Anion exchange uptake of Fe(III) from mixed solvent systems.

TABLE 1

MOLAR CONDUCTANCE VALUES OF THE TMATCF COMPLEX
(ohms⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹)

Solvents	Experimental	Expected	Ranges*
		1 : 1 Electrolyte	1 : 2 Electrolyte
Ethanol	47	35–45	70–90
Methanol	105	80–115	160–220
Acetone	116	100–140	160–200
DMSO	68	37–43	70–80**

* W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, 7, 81.

** M. N. SASTRI and G. S. MURTY, (unpublished results).

Note: The Λ_M values for 1 : 3 electrolytes in DMSO are about 110 (S. K. Ramalingam and S. Soundararajan, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, 29, 1763). Hence the values obtained by us for 1 : 2 electrolytes in this solvent appears reasonable.

characteristics of $FeCl_4^-$ in aqueous and non-aqueous media have been reported by several workers⁸⁻¹⁴. Uri and Breal¹⁵ assigned the peak at 310 nm as characteristic of $FeCl_4^-$ since this peak is fully pronounced

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra of the complex TMATCF (with added chloride).

with added excess of LiCl whereas the peaks at 244 nm and 365 nm are present even prior to the

addition of LiCl. Since our results also conform to those, we proceed on the assumption that the 310 nm peak characterises the FeCl_4^- species. The spectrum in ethanol indicates the existence of FeCl_4^- . On the other hand there is no evidence for the formation of FeCl_4^- in DMSO even when a large concentration of chloride ion was present. In this solvent a single peak is observed at 335 nm. In acetone it has not been possible to identify the peaks in UV region because of strong absorption of the solvent in this region. But the peak at 365 nm showed a significant increase in ϵ with dilution (Table 2).

TABLE 2—MOLAR EXTENSION COEFFICIENT VALUES (ϵ) OF Fe(III) IN ACETONE ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 365 \text{ nm}$)

Fe(III) concentration	ϵ
1.00×10^{-4}	5.10×10^3
8.17×10^{-5}	6.42×10^3
4.08×10^{-5}	7.34×10^3

Such marked alterations in values can be taken as an indication for the existence of polymeric species¹⁶.

Discussion

The aim of this study is to seek an explanation for the anomalous anion exchange behaviour of Fe(III) in the non-aqueous solvent systems DMSO and acetone. The conductivity value for the TMACTCF complex in DMSO shows that the complex does not exist as 1:1 electrolyte but undergoes a change through solute-solvent interaction. The spectrophotometric studies of Drago *et al.*¹⁷ and also our present studies show that FeCl_4^- does not exist in DMSO even in the presence of excess Cl^- concentration. This is also confirmed by our far infrared (200–400 cm^{-1}) spectral studies of the complex as null in DMSO, in which the peak characteristic of FeCl_4^- at 385 cm^{-1} disappeared completely indicating a strong solute-solvent interaction. The spectrophotometric characterisation of Fe(III) species in acetone is not possible because of the fact that the region below 350 nm is strongly absorbed by the solvent. The far infrared spectrum of the complex in MIBK, a less volatile ketone, also shows significant changes indicating a marked solute-solvent interaction.

Lederer¹⁸ subjected Fe(III) in strong HCl to electrophoresis and observed that Fe(III) is present as anionic FeCl_4^- . Subrahmanyam² carried out similar studies with Fe(III) in 85% ethanol—1.0M HCl and established the existence of Fe(III) as anionic FeCl_4^- . But when ethanol is replaced by acetone he observed no movement of the Fe(III) spot indicating that under the conditions Fe(III) exists as uncharged species. Although the conductivity data in acetone indicate a 1:1 electrolyte, it cannot be taken as evidence for the existence of FeCl_4^- since the spectrophotometric evidence at 365 nm peak favours the formation of a polymeric Fe(III) species. A significant observation in our present studies was that the complex TMACTCF could be prepared using only ethanol as solvent and

the yields were almost quantitative. On the other hand, all attempts at preparing this complex using acetone and DMSO as solvents have failed. Further, the pure complex showed high solubilities in these solvents. From these observations we conclude that Fe(III) exists as the anionic FeCl_4^- only in ethanol medium, while in acetone and DMSO the existence of different species has to be assumed.

The general coordination model as applicable to many acids dissolved in nonaqueous polar solvents has been discussed by Meek¹⁹ and Gutman²⁰. The case of FeCl_3 is taken as an example by Meek according to whom several important features of the solvents determine the position of the equilibrium resulting a stepwise replacement of Cl^- ions by solvent molecules. The position of the equilibrium depends upon the ability of each solvent to be associated with the metal ion and to displace the Cl^- ions as schemed below:

It is generally observed that

- (1) the solvents which coordinate strongly with metal ions will replace the halide ligands from the first coordination sphere more extensively than poorly coordinating solvents.
- (2) the more polar strongly coordinating solvents will tend to shift the equilibria towards more complete solvation.

So, from the foregoing discussion it appears that in the case of DMSO, the predominant species of Fe(III) is $[\text{Fe}(\text{DMSO})_5\text{Cl}]^{2+}$ as already established by Drago *et al.*¹⁷ which can account for the non uptake by the anion exchange resin. The predominant species of Fe(III) in acetone may be represented as $(\text{FeCl}_3)_x \cdot \text{S}_y$ which cannot be expected to be taken up by the ion exchanger. The conductivity value corresponding to 1:1 electrolyte observed for the complex in acetone can be explained to arise from the following solute-solvent interaction step, leading to the formation of a 1:1 electrolyte of a different nature.

References

1. I. HAZAN and J. KORKISCH, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1965, 32, 46.
2. J. SUBRAHMANYAM, Ph.D. Thesis, Andhra University, Waltair, India, 1966.

3. J. S. FRITZ and M. L. GILLETTE, *Talanta*, 1968, 15, 287.
4. A. P. RAO and S. P. DUBEY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 396.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman ELBS, 1964, p. 444.
6. F. A. COTTON, D. M. L. GOODGAME and M. GOODGAME, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4690.
7. R. A. HORNE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, 61, 1651.
8. D. E. METZLER and R. J. MYERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 3776.
9. R. J. MYERS, D. E. METZLER and E. H. SWIFT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 3767.
10. D. A. GAMLEN and D. O. JORDAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1435.
11. Y. MARCUS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear. Chem.*, 1960, 12, 287.
12. N. H. NACHTRIEB and J. G. CONWAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3547.
13. J. S. FRIEDMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 4.
14. G. W. BRADY, M. B. ROBIN and J. VARIMBI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 1168.
15. N. URI and G. J. BREALEY, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1952, 20, 257.
16. G. W. LATIMER and N. H. FURMAN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1962, 14, 729.
17. R. S. DRAGO, D. M. HART and R. L. CARLSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 87, 1900.
18. M. LEDERER and F. L. WARD, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1952, 6, 355.
19. D. W. MEEK, "Chemistry of non-aqueous solvents", (Ed. S. J. Lagowski), Academic Press, 1966, p. 17.
20. V. GUTMAN, "Coordination chemistry in non-aqueous solutions", Springer-Verlag, 1968, p. 24.